

Using the Julia programming language to calculate the equilibrium composition of a multicomponent gas phase system

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Abstract. The method, algorithm and text of the program for calculating the equilibrium composition of a multicomponent gas-phase system in the Julia language are presented. Examples of using the program are given.

1. Introduction

The problem of calculation the equilibrium composition of chemically reacting thermodynamic systems has long attracted the attention of many researchers, since it has a significant applied value [1-3]. The first computer-oriented algorithms for solving this problem were proposed back in the 50s of the last century [4, 5]. An overview of the basic methods for calculating equilibrium in homogeneous thermodynamic systems can be found in the monographs [6, 7]. This paper presents a modified algorithm for calculating the equilibrium in a multicomponent homogeneous thermodynamic system, developed by Professor of Bauman Moscow State Technical University B.G. Trusov [8], and its software implementation in the programming language Julia (julialang.org). When implementing the algorithm, the materials of the Appendix to the textbook on linear algebra [9] were used. The monograph [10] contains the text of the program for calculating the equilibrium of a multicomponent heterogeneous system in the Fortran language, but it is rather complicated to understand. Therefore, this paper provides a significantly simplified version of the program, which is easy to study and modify if necessary. We chose Julia for the implementation of the algorithm, since it is a highly efficient free programming language focused on solving scientific and technical problems [11].

The article is structured as follows . A description of the method and algorithm for calculating the equilibrium composition and the call of the function of equilibrium calculation function MicPV is given, then it is described how one can prepare the initial data for calculating the equilibrium. The Appendix contains the text of the program and examples of its use.

1. Theory

Consider a thermodynamic system formed by a mixture of ideal gases. The state of a thermodynamic system, characterized by the invariance of parameters in time and the absence of flows under constant external conditions, is usually called equilibrium. We can

assume that equilibrium is some limiting state to which the isolated from external influences thermodynamic system tends. The isolation condition in this case means that the rate of relaxation processes inside the system is greater than the rate of change of parameters at its boundaries. In turn, in the equilibrium state, the entropy of the isolated system is maximal. Thus, the solution of the problem of calculating the equilibrium composition assumes the need to determine the coordinates of the conditional maximum of entropy

$$S(U, V, \vec{n}) \rightarrow \max, \quad (1)$$

subject to the constraints of constancy of internal energy and volume, mass balance, and nonnegativity of the number of moles of substances

$$U = \text{const}, V = \text{const},$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^k a_{ji} n_i = b_j, j=1, 2, \dots, m,$$

$$n_i \geq 0, i=1, 2, \dots, k,$$

k – the number of substances in the system, m – the number of chemical elements in the system, a_{ji} – the number of atoms of element j in the molecule of substance i , b_j – the content of element j in the system.

To determine the coordinates of the constrained maximum of entropy, we will use the method of Lagrange multipliers. Let's write the Lagrange function as follows

$$\Lambda = S + \sum_{j=1}^m \lambda_j \left(\sum_{i=1}^k a_{ji} n_i - b_j \right).$$

The coordinates of the conditional maximum of entropy are determined by the following system of equations

$$\left(\frac{\partial S}{\partial n_i} \right)_{U, V, n_{j \neq i}} + \sum_{j=1}^m a_{ji} \lambda_j = 0, i=1, 2, \dots, k,$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^k a_{ji} n_i = b_j, j=1, 2, \dots, m.$$

As it follows from the fundamental Gibbs equation $TdS = dU + pdV - \sum_{i=1}^k \mu_i dn_i$,

$$\left(\frac{\partial S}{\partial n_i} \right)_{U, V, n_{j \neq i}} = -\frac{\mu_i}{T},$$

so we got a system of equations

$$-\frac{\mu_i}{T} + \sum_{j=1}^m a_{ji} \lambda_j = 0, i=1, 2, \dots, k, \quad (2)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^k a_{ji} n_i = b_j, j=1,2,\dots,m \quad . \quad (3)$$

For ideal gas

$\mu_i = \mu_i^\circ(T) + RT \ln \bar{p}_i$, $\mu_i^\circ(T) = H_i^\circ(T) - TS_i^\circ(T)$, $\bar{p}_i = \bar{p} \cdot n_i / n_\Sigma$, $\bar{p} = p / p^\circ$, p° - standard pressure.

Thus, for given values of temperature and pressure, the system of equations can be represented as follows

$$\ln n_i - \ln \frac{n_\Sigma}{\bar{p}} - \sum_j a_{ji} \lambda_j = -\frac{\mu_i^\circ}{RT} \quad , \quad (4)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^k a_{ji} n_i = b_j, j=1,2,\dots,m \quad , \quad (5)$$

$$n_\Sigma = \sum_{i=1}^k n_i \quad . \quad (6)$$

Unknown are the equilibrium concentrations of substances n_i , the total amount of gas moles n_Σ and values of Lagrange multipliers λ_j .

Replace $\ln n_i$ with x_i , then $n_i = \exp(x_i)$, $\ln \frac{\bar{p}}{n_\Sigma}$ replace with $y = \ln \frac{RT}{V}$. Now we can write (4) as follows

$$x_i = -y + \sum_j a_{ji} \lambda_j - \frac{\mu_i^\circ}{RT} \quad \text{and} \quad \exp(x_i) = \exp\left(-y + \sum_j a_{ji} \lambda_j - \frac{\mu_i^\circ}{RT}\right) \quad .$$

It was proposed in [8], to write the last relation in the form of an approximate equality

$\exp(x_i) \approx \exp(x_{0i}) \left(-y + \sum_j a_{ji} \lambda_j - \frac{\mu_i^\circ}{RT} + 1 - x_{0i}\right)$, where subscript 0 denotes the iterative value of an unknown quantity.

With this in mind, the mass balance equation (5) can be represented as follows

$$\sum_{i=1}^k a_{ji} \exp(x_i) \approx \sum_{i=1}^k a_{ji} \exp(x_{0i}) \left(-y + \sum_j a_{ji} \lambda_j - \frac{\mu_i^\circ}{RT} + 1 - x_{0i}\right) = b_j, j=1,2,\dots,m \quad . \quad (7)$$

The unknowns in (7) are the Lagrange multipliers λ_j and the variable y .

We will assume that the temperature is known, the value of either pressure or volume is given, and the behavior of the gas phase is described by the equation of state of an ideal gas of the form

$$p \exp(-y) = \sum_{i=1}^k \exp(x_i) \quad .$$

For given values of temperature and volume, the equality holds

$$y = \ln \frac{RT}{V} , \quad (8)$$

if pressure is set, B.G. Trusov proposed to use the approximate equality in the calculation

$$y p \exp(-y_0) + \sum_{i=1}^k \exp(x_i) = p \exp(-y_0)(1 + y_0) , \quad (9)$$

here the subscript 0 also denotes the iterative value of an unknown quantity.

To find the solution of the system of nonlinear equations (7)-(9) the Newton-Raphson method is used.

2. Description of the equilibrium calculation function MicPV

To call the function the following syntax is used:

```
iertxt, Parameters, EquilibriumComposition =  
MPV.MicPV(temperature, pressure, volume, m, k, b, Nji, F) ,
```

where

iertxt – the text message about the termination of the program, if the calculation is completed without errors it is an empty string;

Parameters – vector containing four parameters: pressure (MPa), temperature (K), volume (m³), number of moles of the gas phase;

EquilibriumComposition – vector containing the equilibrium composition in moles;

temperature - value temperature in K;

pressure – value of pressure in MPa;

volume – volume, cub m³;

m – the number of chemical elements from which the thermodynamic system is formed;

k – the number of substances included in the thermodynamic system;

b – vector containing amounts of chemical elements (*m* values);

Nji – two-dimensional array of values a_{ji} (*k* rows, *m* columns);

F – vector containing dimensionless values $-\frac{\mu_i^\circ}{RT}$.

The text of the function from the entry point to the start of the iteration cycle (*while true*) contains operators in which the vectors are zeroed and the initial approximations of unknown equilibrium concentrations are set. Next, the matrix *S* and the vector *bb* are filled. It is assumed that systems of linear equations has the form: $S^*xx=bb$, where *xx* – vector of unknowns having length *m*+1 (first *m* values are Lagrange

multipliers, the last is y value). The system of linear equations is solved using QR decomposition [9]. This method allows us to solve the problem of the degeneracy of the matrix S, which may be caused by the fact that the amount of independent (by Gibbs) components is less than the number of chemical elements. For example, if the thermodynamic system is formed by carbon and oxygen in a molar ratio of 1:2, then at room temperature and atmospheric pressure, the independent component is carbon dioxide i.e., there is only CO₂ in measurable amount in the equilibrium system, concentrations of other components are negligibly small. The mass balance equations (5) have the form

$$n_{\text{CO}_2}=1$$

$$2n_{\text{CO}_2}=2,$$

Obviously, in this case one of the equations is superfluous. Checking for possible degeneracy is performed in the function **back_subst**, which is given in [9] and slightly modified to solve our problem.

Once an iterative solution is obtained, it is adjusted to ensure the convergence. At the same time, the maximum relative difference between the current and previous solutions is calculated. If the difference does not exceed the specified value, the convergence conditions are checked.

3. Verification of convergence conditions

The convergence conditions are checked in the function **CheckConvergency**. The conditions of mass balance (5), the condition of phase stability and the condition of the duality theorem [12] are checked.

The phase stability condition has the form [13]

$$\sum_{i=1}^k \exp\left(-\frac{\mu_i^\circ}{RT} - \ln \bar{p} + \sum_j a_{ji} \lambda_j\right) = 1 \quad .$$

According to the duality theorem the following relation must be satisfied for the solution found [12]

$$\sum_{j=1}^m b_j \lambda_j = \sum_{i=1}^k n_i (\mu_i^\circ + RT \ln \bar{p}_i) \quad .$$

4. On the calculation of chemical potential in standard conditions

To calculate the chemical potential under standard conditions, it is necessary to know the corresponding values of enthalpy and entropy. In the reference book TSIV [14, 15], information on the thermodynamic properties of individual substances is given in the form of tables and coefficients of the approximating polynomial f_i , with the help of which

the temperature dependence of entropy and enthalpy changes at a given temperature can be calculated by the formulas

$$S^\circ(T) = f_1 + f_2(\ln X + 1) - f_3/X^2 + 2f_5X + 3f_6X^2 + 4f_7X^3, \text{ J}/(\text{mol}\cdot\text{K}),$$

$$H^\circ(T) - H^\circ(0) = T(f_2 - 2f_3/X^2 - f_4/X + f_5X + 2f_6X^2 + 3f_7X^3), \text{ J}/\text{mol},$$

where $X = T/10000$. The standard pressure in the reference book TSIV p° equals 1 atm (101325 Pa).

The enthalpy value can be calculated by the formula

$$H^\circ(T) = \Delta_f H^\circ(298.15) + H^\circ(T) - H^\circ(0) - [H^\circ(298.15) - H^\circ(0)] .$$

The reference book NIST Chemistry Webbook (<http://webbook.nist.gov>) gives the coefficients of similar relations for approximating the temperature dependence of thermodynamic functions in the form

$$S^\circ(T) = A \ln(t) + Bt + Ct^2/2 + Dt^3/3 - E/(2t^2) + G,$$

$$H^\circ(T) = H^\circ(298.15) + At + Bt^2/2 + Ct^3/3 + Dt^4/4 - E/t + F - H,$$

$t = T/1000$; A, B, C, D, E, F, G, H – polynomial coefficients, J-mol-K. Standard pressure p° equals 1 bar.

Conclusion

The text of the program, examples of the data and the use of the **MicPV** function are given in [16]. To test the program, the Julia 1.3 was used. The text of the program is small and easy to understand. It can be used both for educational purposes and for solving the applied problems. The program can be easily improved using the real gas equation of state, the corresponding algorithm is presented in [17].

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